

Raster images: A guide to good practice

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Contents

1. Introduction to raster images	5
1.1 What are raster images?.....	5
Areas of application	6
1.2 Things to consider.....	6
2. Things to consider when creating raster images	7
2.1 General considerations.....	7
Resolution	7
Bit depth	8
Colour space	8
Compression	9
Transparency	9
Layers	10
Other considerations	10
3. Archiving raster images	11
3.1 Deciding what should be preserved	11
3.2 Deciding how it should be preserved	11
Significant properties.....	12
Recommended file formats	12
3.3 Metadata and documentation.....	13
4. File format.....	15
5. Bibliography	21

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1. Introduction to raster images

Images appear in many contexts and can be used for different purposes. An image is usually a two-dimensional representation of something and may form the empirical data material in a context or, for example, be used as an educational and visual aid for example. There are two main image file formats used to describe digital images. These are usually referred to as raster images (sometimes also called bitmaps) or vector images. Both image file formats have their advantages and disadvantages. For example, the vector format handles enlargement better than the raster format (see Figure 1) but is not able to represent colour nuances as accurately. The most common type of raster images are digital photographs, while vector images are mainly used in GIS and CAD. This guide aims to provide guidance on what to consider when preserving raster images. For guidance on handling vector images, see our guide in the same series: *Vector images: a guide to good practice*.

The guide covers the most common file formats used for storing digital image files and which formats are suitable for archiving. It will also discuss the archival strategies that may be used to ensure that the quality of the image files is maintained. Although some basic technical descriptions will be given in the guide, it is not intended to provide a more in-depth account of the technical specifications of raster images.

Vektor Raster

Figure 1: The difference between enlarged vector and raster images. The vector image remains sharp after enlargement, while the raster image is perceived as pixelated and blurred.

1.1 What are raster images?

A raster image (see Figure 2) is made up of a large number of small squares (pixels) that together form a grid, with each square having its own unique location and colour. Raster images can be created in many ways, for example by digital camera photography, by scanning, or by other working processes, such as images generated from GIS layouts.

Figure 2: Representation of points, lines and polygons as vectors or rasters.

Areas of application

Raster images are common in research projects and appear in all contexts in which there is a need for images. How the images are used may vary. They may be the empirical data analysed in the research project but may also be used as visual tools to document working processes and results, or in connection with publications.

This guide aims to cover the most common types of raster image created through research, including:

- Digital photographs
- Digital images created by scanning
- Exported data, or screenshots from various vector applications
- Original images such as illustrations and posters

1.2 Things to consider

A problem with raster images is that there is a wide range of formats available. File formats vary widely in terms of functionality and availability, covering a spectrum of format types from proprietary,¹ application-specific formats to open standards of various kinds. For example, different formats handle compression (destructive or lossless), colour depth, transparency support and embedded metadata in different ways. Therefore, it is important for data creators to store their images in an appropriate file format, both when the image is created and when it is archived. Images in some project workflows may change format depending on how they are used. Data creators therefore need to be aware of what metadata there are, what range of functionality each format supports, and what might be lost in a format migration.

¹ Proprietary file formats are file formats that have restrictions (usually set by the owner) on how they can be used, modified, or copied.

2. Things to consider when creating raster images

2.1 General considerations

Although functionality may vary between formats, there are a number of functions that remain constant and should be considered when creating and processing image files. As with many other file types, it is not possible to specify an exact setting for these functions. Instead, there needs to be a strategy adapted to the purpose of the project that includes the images. For many of the properties described below, data creators rarely need to manually perform different settings. Instead, there are predefined default settings that computer programs and digital cameras use. It is important to be aware that these properties exist, are important and may vary (what is standard for one camera model may not necessarily be the same for another model), but that they may not be inadequate for what you want to achieve with your images. To ensure that the images you take for a project are of adequate quality, you should therefore take some aspects into consideration.

Resolution

Essentially, resolution describes the level of detail in an image expressed as a pixel count (pixels per inch [ppi], dots per inch [dpi] or samples per inch [spi]). The higher the resolution, the more detail is captured in the image and consequently the larger the file size. It may therefore be necessary to balance the level of detail required for an image against the size of the file created. Raster images are sensitive to changes in size. It is usually possible to reduce the size of a raster image without any problems, but if you try to enlarge the image, the sharpness will deteriorate, and the image may be perceived as pixelated and blurred (compare the images in Figure 3). Therefore, an original image should never be compressed as this will cause the resolution of the image to deteriorate permanently. Instead, compressed copies can be created from an uncompressed original.

Figure 3: Same image, different resolution. Left: 72 ppi (1268 kb) and right: 15 ppi (81 kb).

Bit depth

Bit depth refers to how many shades of colour an image file can contain, or how many bits a computer uses to represent colours displayed on a screen. Images can vary in bit depth from, for example, 1 bit (i.e., either black or white) to 2 bits (usually grayscale) to 24 bits (standard colour), etc. As with resolution, it is important to consider bit depth in relation to the purpose of the image and choose one that stores all the information required, while minimizing file size.

Bit depth and colours			
Bits	Colours per channel	Bit depth (RGB)	Number of possible shades of colour
1	2	3-bit RGB	8
2	4	6-bit RGB	64
3	8	9-bit RGB	512
4	16	12-bit RGB	4,096
5	32	15-bit RGB	32,768
6	64	18-bit RGB	262,144
8	256	24-bit RGB	16,777,216
12	4,096	36-bit RGB	Approximately 68.7 billion

Colour space

Colour space should be considered in addition to bit depth. Colour space is a way of describing the colours and shades of colour which the user has access to and can use. Common colour systems include RGB (Red, Green, Blue) and CMYK (Cyan, Magenta and Yellow with the addition of black [Key colour]) for colour images, or binary (black and white) and grayscale formats for black and white images. In addition to ensuring that the most appropriate system is used for the image, one distinction between them is that RGB systems are primarily used for images intended to be viewed on a monitor and the CMYK system is used for printing. RGB systems can contain more colour combinations than the CMYK system, so it is important to be aware that RGB-based images may not have the correct colour properties when printed. There are RGB systems that work well for printing (Adobe RGB, for example), but the overall recommendation is to use CMYK for printing. In general, digital cameras produce images with RGB colour and if these are later incorporated in a publication, there is a potential risk that the colour information will be wrong. Because RGB is so well established, many printers accept RGB and automatically convert the images to CMYK format for printing, but there is a risk of the printed images looking faded. To have more control over images that will be used primarily for printing and to preserve the colour properties, it is best to convert to CMYK in advance.

Colour spaces have their own coordinate system and place shades of colour based on coordinates. Therefore, there may be several colour systems that can handle (roughly) the same number of possible shades, but where the same shade has different coordinates. There are several competing

versions of the RGB colour system. The most common standard is sRGB, but Adobe RGB and Prophoto RGB are also relatively common standards. The reason sRGB appears most frequently is that it is a smaller colour space than the other two, and until a few years ago it was expensive for monitor manufacturers to build displays that could accurately reproduce colour spaces larger than sRGB. They decided to restrict production to the smallest standardized RGB colour space. As with transitions from RGB to CMYK, transformations from one RGB system to another may result in images looking washed out and faded in other applications or on the internet.

Figure 4: The primary colours cyan, magenta, and yellow are mixed in varying degrees to produce other colours. Mixing all three primary colours in equal amounts should, theoretically, result in black.

Compression

Applications that generate digital photographs and other colour images of high complexity can produce exceptionally large file sizes. The lack of storage space and the need to be able to transfer image data quickly over the internet, among other things, have led to the development of a range of image compression techniques to reduce the size of image files. Most compression techniques are independent of specific file formats. In fact, many formats can support a number of different compression types, and these are an important part of digital image creation, use and storage (Brown 2009:4). Raster image compression may be either destructive (lossy) or lossless. Destructive compression means that some of the information is lost, and the file becomes smaller in size. Since image quality deteriorates in destructive compression, it is important to know what type of compression different file formats use. An example of a common format that uses destructive compression is JPEG. Examples of lossless file formats are TIFF and PNG. These allow data to be stored without compression. Destructive compression techniques should be treated with caution. If images are repeatedly migrated between different loss formats, the image quality deteriorates with each migration. However, in some circumstances the use of destructive compression may be required, for example to allow large volumes of high-resolution colour images to be managed economically. In such circumstances, visually lossless compression should be used, a compression method that does not adversely affect image quality (Brown 2009:5).

Transparency

Image transparency, i.e., elements of an image that are transparent, is supported by the vast majority of vector formats, but only by some raster formats (for example TIFF, PNG, BMP, JPEG2000, and GIF). While this is a minor consideration, it is important to be aware that transparent elements of an image are not supported by all formats. Methods of achieving transparency vary between formats. Commonly, a colour space called RGBA is used, where A stands for Alpha. The alpha

channel does not describe a colour. It is transparent and determines the degree of transparency of a pixel. Where RGBA is used, an image may contain transparent fields (transparent holes). This means that such an image can be used in an image processing application that works with layers (for example Adobe Photoshop) and, if the image is placed as a layer on top of another image, the underlying image will be visible in the transparent voids.

Layers

Layers are a common feature of many popular image processing applications and are used to allow parts of an image to be processed/edited independently of other parts. The use of layers is not supported by raster file formats. If a data creator has used layers during the image processing stage, these layers will be merged, and it will no longer be possible to export or process individual layers.

Other considerations

The elements described above vary in importance depending on the type of raster image being created. If the raster image is in the form of a digital photo, a data creator is able to make certain choices in the digital camera even before the images are taken. For example, most digital cameras are able to save images in a custom raw format (for more information, see section 4. *File format*) or as JPEG and then the photographer can choose the resolution. The data creator must then decide what is most appropriate for the project. If the images are to be submitted for archiving (or if you are unsure about file size and resolution), you are recommended to save the images in an uncompressed state with the highest possible resolution. This makes the files larger, which may in itself cause problems, but the advantage of a high-resolution, uncompressed image is that there is no risk of information being lost. In addition, compressed copies can be created from an uncompressed original.

Many cameras provide the option of taking black and white or grayscale photographs. Consideration should then be given to whether these settings should be used at the time of shooting, or whether the images should be taken in colour and later converted to black and white/grayscale using an image processing application.

If raster images are created by other means than photography (raster images can be generated in many different applications), it is also important to choose the appropriate resolution, bit depth and colour space for the dataset being generated. The same applies if the images are generated using a document scanner. Many scanned files undergo a subsequent conversion, such as conversion to PDF files, which may result in a reduction in resolution. If this is the case, it is important for the original files to have an adequately high resolution so that such compression does not result in excessive loss of information.

There may be a need to export vector-based data as raster images. Data created in vector applications (for example for GIS or CAD) has no fixed resolution. If a data creator decides to create a raster file, the resolution will be fixed for the vector image, resulting in the loss of some functionality and layers. It is therefore important for an appropriate resolution to be chosen for the raster image, depending on the intended use of the image and, if possible, for the original vector file also to be stored in a format in which the associated information is preserved.

3. Archiving raster images

3.1 Deciding what should be preserved

Deciding what to preserve depends on how and for what purpose the raster images were created. The quality of the images should be such that they are suitable for archiving, for example by choosing the right file format. The general recommendation is to archive the original raster images in an uncompressed open format, if possible.

- Digital cameras often provide limited options in terms of file types that can be created. For a data creator, this may mean that the original images can be created as JPEG or TIFF or in raw format (RAW).² If the data creator chooses JPEG, they should also make informed decisions about the degree of compression. If a raw format is chosen, the data creator must ensure that the files can be converted into an appropriate archive format. TIFF is preferred, but TIFF files are comparatively large.
- Scanners often allow the user to choose the format in which the scanned image will be saved. It is recommended that scanned images, before processing and regardless of the final format, be saved in an open, uncompressed format (or a format that uses lossless compression).
- When raster images are created in an application, the user usually has to select the format in which the exported image will be saved. Most applications support a wide range of formats. For files exported from software such as GIS or CAD, the choice of file formats may be limited. If it is not possible to select, for example, TIFF, the files can be converted into a suitable archive format in other applications. If possible, try to choose a format that does not use destructive compression.
- Many files, especially digital photographs, allow metadata to be embedded in the file format. These can be useful both as file documentation and for future reuse. There are also image processing applications that use embedded metadata to perform the image processing (for example Agisoft PhotoScan). In most cases where such metadata exists, it is useful to retain and archive it.

3.2 Deciding how it should be preserved

In many cases, digital images to be archived need to be converted into a stable format for preservation. If composite images³ have been created in an image processing application (for example Photoshop or Photo-Paint), it may be worth saving the individual images that make up the composite image as separate archive files, in addition to saving the final merged version of the file. Such a strategy can also be applied to simple animated image files such as GIF files where each *frame* (each frame in a GIF animation is a still image) can be exported to a separate file in a preservation format.

² Raw format (RAW) is an unprocessed file that must be converted by a RAW converter before it can be displayed in an image processor. Digital cameras normally have an integrated converter. The raw format contains all the information needed to create an image. The format saves all the information captured by the sensor with information about the photograph (for example metadata). If you save in raw format, you can make more precise adjustments later before creating the image. If you save directly in jpg, for example, all information that that format does not need is discarded.

³ A composite image is an image in which two or more images are combined to create a single image.

Significant properties

The most significant properties of raster images are described below.

- **Image size and resolution** – when converting, make sure that the original resolution and image size are the same in the file format chosen for preservation. In addition, it is important that destructive compression is not applied to the image when converting it to a new format.
- **Bit depth and colour space** – you should ensure that the bit depth and colour space of the original image are supported in the preservation format and that the image quality does not deteriorate when the image is converted.

Although these properties are present in all image formats, it is important that the properties remain the same/maintain the same values when images are converted into an archive format.

Recommended file formats

The file formats described below are those recommended for preservation of image files:

Format	Description
TIFF 6.0 (.tif/.tiff)	Recommended for preserving digital raster images and includes support for Exif metadata. ⁴ Other formats based on the format, such as TIFF/EP and GeoTIFF, are also recommended as preservation formats.
Digital Negative, DNG (.dng)	The Adobe DNG format is recommended for storing raw image data (mainly from digital photographs). DNG is an open extension of the TIFF format and supports Exif, IPTC, ⁵ and XMP metadata. ⁶
JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg)	Suitable for preserving digital photographs unless they were originally created in another uncompressed format. A data creator can also set the JPEG format not to compress the file.
JPEG2000 (.jp2)	A data creator has the option of selecting that JPEG2000 will use non-destructive compression, and the format is therefore suitable for preservation where the images need to be compressed.
PNG (.png)	Suitable for preserving image files that are only to be displayed on a monitor and not printed on paper. PNG is an open standard and supports Exif metadata.

⁴ Exchangeable image file format (Exif) is a specification developed for storing raster images in digital cameras. The specification includes the storage of both images and sound as digital cameras today can easily handle the digitization of both media. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Exif>, last visited 25 August 2022.

⁵ <https://iptc.org/standards/photo-metadata/iptc-standard/>, last visited 25 August 2022.

⁶ <https://www.adobe.com/products/xmp.html>, last visited 25 August 2022.

3.3 Metadata and documentation

Most digital cameras can store metadata in what is known as *EXchangeable Image File Format* (Exif), and it can be accessed via many image processing applications. Exif is a specification based on metadata being stored with the file format, which in practical terms means that image features are automatically recorded and stored in the image file for use in, for example, archiving. Camera manufacturers also save most of the camera's settings, including model, version, image rotation, aperture, shutter, focal length, white balance, light metering method, ISO, whether the flash was used, distance from the subject, and anything else related to the moment in which the photo was taken. Previously, Exif did not support JPEG2000 and PNG, but now Exif supports most of the most common file formats. Users can add their own metadata to Exif, such as the name of the originator. This can be done to varying degrees in image processing applications, via various websites online, or under the image properties in Explorer. Embedded metadata such as Exif may in some cases be crucial to understanding an image. If deemed applicable, the metadata should be exported to a separate file (as a text file or XML file and stored with the image file). Otherwise, there is a risk of loss or corruption during subsequent migration. One problem with the specification is that image processing applications do not always handle Exif data correctly. If the image is modified, the information may be destroyed or distorted. There is also a risk of some metadata elements (for example date) containing incorrect information and the data creator needs to be aware of this.

In addition to Exif, there is also IPTC, which is another image metadata standard. IPTC usually processes more general metadata that may either be embedded in the image file itself or stored in a separate file. Such metadata is intended to record descriptive and administrative data such as the creator, title, and content.

The metadata elements listed below mainly describe technical aspects. More general metadata is listed first. This may apply to a single image, and also to entire sets of multiple images. More specific metadata needed for each individual image is then presented.

Properties	Description
For each set of images	
Project name	Name of the project.
Originator	Name of the data creator.
Date	Date on which the image(s) was(were) taken.
Number of images	The total number of images submitted for preservation.
Camera/scanner specifications	Make and model of the camera and lens, or scanner, used.
Copyright	Who owns the files and how may they be used?
Supplementary notes	Any supplementary notes.

Properties	Description
For each individual image	
Image file name	File name and file extension.
Description of location and orientation	Describe the location in general terms and the relationship of the camera to the object (for example facing south).
Image description	Description of the image.
File format and version	For example, TIFF 6.0.
File size	Size of the file in bytes.
Resolution	Image resolution measured in <i>pixels per inch</i> (ppi).
Dimensions	Image size measured in pixels, for example 400 x 700 px.
Colour space	For example, RGB, or grayscale.
Bit depth	For example, 24-bit or 8-bit.
Software	Software in which the image was created (for example for scanned images, or images created in GIS applications).
Format conversions (if any have been done)	List of any format changes to the digital images and the software used.

4. File format

The tables below describe some common file formats for storing digital raster images and the formats that are recommended for archiving. Some of these formats may appear obsolete, but they are described here because it may be necessary to handle older file formats:

Adobe Photoshop document file	
File format/extension	PSD/.psd
Format	Adobe Photoshop document file is a proprietary file format owned by Adobe. PSD is primarily used as a working file for processing images.
Description	<i>The PSD format is very flexible and supports the use of masks and layers, transparency, text, and a number of other functions that make it an ideal format for creating and editing images. It also supports Exif, IPTC, and XMP metadata. PSD has limited compression support and files therefore tend to be large. The PSD format is ideal for creating and editing files, but its proprietary, closed nature means that there is limited third-party support and it is therefore unsuitable for archiving. It is a good idea for a copy of a PSD file to accompany the original file (which should be in a different format, preferably TIFF or DNG) so that future editing is possible, if required.</i>
Recommendations	Not suitable for dissemination or archiving.

Bit-Mapped Graphics format (BMP)	
File format/extension	BMP/.bmp
Format	<i>Bit-Mapped Graphics Format</i> is an image file format created and owned by Microsoft.
Description	<i>BMP is basically only used with Windows and DOS operating systems. The BMP format is similar to the GIF file format (see the table for GIF later in the document) and works well for simple raster graphics. The format supports some types of compression, although not as efficiently as GIF. Since an uncompressed BMP image has such a simple structure, BMP is supported by many image viewing/processing applications and browsers. BMP provides limited options for embedding metadata.</i>
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination, but not for archiving.

Digital Negative (DNG)

File format/extension	DNG/.dng
Format	<i>DNG</i> , or <i>Digital Negative</i> , is a file format developed by Adobe Systems for raw digital raster images (RAW).
Description	<i>DNG</i> is a non-proprietary, freely available extension of <i>TIFF 6.0</i> with support for <i>Exif</i> , <i>IPTC</i> and <i>XMP metadata</i> . The format was developed by Adobe Systems in response to many camera manufacturers developing their own, incompatible formats for raw data for digital cameras. The Adobe <i>DNG format</i> is the recommended format for storing raw image data (mainly for digital photos).
Recommendations	Suitable for the dissemination and archiving of raw data files (RAW).

Graphics Interchange Format (GIF)

File format/extension	GIF/.gif
Format	<i>Graphics Interchange Format</i> is a proprietary format developed by CompuServe.
Description	The <i>GIF format</i> is used for both still images and simple animations and uses lossless compression. The format has a limited palette (8 bits/256 colours) and limited options for embedding metadata. The format is widely used on the internet and has gained in popularity in recent years as it can be used to create short animations. There are other, more suitable formats for storing two-dimensional still images.
Recommendations	Owing to the limited palette of the format and the limited options for metadata storage, other formats should be chosen before <i>GIF</i> . Not suitable for dissemination or archiving.

JPEG	
File format/extension	JPEG/.jpg, .jpeg
Format	<i>JPEG</i> is an ISO standard format ⁷ that was developed in 1990 by the Joint Photographic Expert Group.
Description	The <i>JPEG format</i> was originally intended primarily for digital photographs. The format offers 32-bit bit depth and uses visually lossless compression that removes information that is not perceptible to the human eye using a technique called Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). ⁸ In practice, this only works for certain types of digital image (for digital photos it works relatively well). For raster images created from vector data, the compression may cause visible deterioration. At the same time, the specification provides options for the user to set the compression ratio. This allows the user to make trade-offs between compression ratio and image quality: the higher the setting, the better the quality of the finished image, but at the cost of a larger file size (Brown 2009:7). <i>JPEG</i> also allows <i>Exif</i> and <i>IPTC metadata</i> to be embedded in the file. There is a lossless version of the format (<i>JPEG_LS</i> , ISO/IEC 14495-1:1994 and -2:2003), ⁹ but as the format has not caught on there are very few applications that can use it, so it is not recommended.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination (where high-resolution, uncompressed images are not necessary) and archiving.
File format/extension	JPEG2000/.jp2, .jpx
Format	<i>JPEG2000</i> is an ISO standard ¹⁰ and is intended to replace the <i>JPEG</i> format.
Description	The development of <i>JPEG2000</i> has been slow since the format was released in December 2000 and it still lacks web support. There are very few digital cameras that take photographs in the <i>JPEG2000 format</i> , and many image viewing/processing applications still do not support it. Compared to <i>JPEG</i> , <i>JPEG2000</i> provides the ability to effectively compress the image resolution without reducing the image size. The format also differs from <i>JPEG</i> in that it uses XML (the <i>JPX format</i>) to store metadata in the file. Nevertheless, the format is considered suitable for archiving, thanks to its use of lossless compression and scalability, and it is used worldwide in archives and libraries for digital raster images.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and archiving.

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/18902.html>, last visited 25 August 2022.

⁸ <https://se.mathworks.com/help/images/discrete-cosine-transform.html>, last visited 25 August 2022.

⁹ <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000151.shtml>, last visited 26 August 2022.

¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/78321.html>, last visited 25 August 2022.

Portable Network Graphics (PNG)	
File format/extension	PNG/.png
Format	<i>Portable Network Graphics</i> (PNG) was developed in 1996 and is an open ISO standard ¹¹ supported by the W3C.
Description	<i>PNG</i> is intended to replace the <i>GIF format</i> and offers 32-bit colour depth, lossless compression, support for an Alpha channel (transparency) and a host of other functions. As the format is mainly designed for internet use, it does not support CMYK. The format offers some advantages over <i>JPEG</i> (for example less visible artefacts). <i>PNG</i> supports <i>Exif</i> metadata.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and archiving.

TIFF	
File format/extension	TIFF 6.0/.tif, .tiff
Format	<i>Tagged Image File Format</i> (TIFF) 6.0 is a file format for raster images, developed in 1986 by Aldus Corporation, Microsoft, and Hewlett-Packard.
Description	There are several different versions of <i>TIFF</i> . Some of these use destructive compression and are therefore not suitable for archiving. <i>TIFF 6.0</i> is a widely accepted file format for digital raster images that uses lossless compression. The format supports <i>Exif metadata</i> and includes header tags (information on size, image data order, any image compression) that define the geometry of the image. <i>TIFF</i> is a popular format among graphic artists and photographers.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and archiving, depending on the compression method.
File format/extension	TIFF/EP/.tif, .tiff
Format	<i>Tagged Image File Format/Electronic Photography</i> (TIFF/EP). An ISO standardized file format based on <i>TIFF 6.0</i> .
Description	<i>TIFF/EP</i> is a standard format for digital raster images. The format is based on <i>TIFF 6.0</i> and has the same file extensions and header tags as <i>TIFF</i> . The format

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/29581.html>, last visited 25 August 2022.

	also shares some common concepts and metadata tags with <i>Exif</i> . The format can be compressed using both destructive and lossless methods and for archiving it is recommended that all compression is lossless. The format was developed as a raw format for cameras, but DNG, which is more or less identical, has been more widely used.
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and archiving, depending on the compression method.
File format/extension	GeoTIFF/.tif, .tiff
Format	<i>GeoTIFF</i> is a <i>TIFF file format</i> that allows geographical reference information to be embedded in the file.
Description	<i>GeoTIFF</i> allows map projections, coordinate systems, ellipsoids, and reference systems to be embedded in a .tif file. The <i>GeoTIFF format</i> is equivalent to <i>TIFF 6.0</i> , which means that even software that cannot read and interpret spatial metadata will be able to open a <i>GeoTIFF file</i> as a standard <i>TIFF 6.0</i> . <i>GeoTIFF</i> should not be confused with the <i>TFW format</i> . ¹² This format uses two files, a .tif file and a .tfw 'world' file to provide georeferenced information. <i>TFW</i> is different from <i>GeoTIFF</i> .
Recommendations	Suitable for dissemination and archiving, depending on the compression method.

RAW

File format/extension	Raw (may have a large number of file extensions)
Format	Raw is not a single format. It is a generic term for unprocessed raster image files. Many manufacturers have their own proprietary raw formats.
Description	Raw files are unprocessed raster image files in a number of different formats created directly by a digital camera. The name 'Raw' comes from the fact that image files in RAW format are completely unprocessed and therefore not ready to be edited in an image processor or printed. Owing to the lack of standardization it is almost impossible to characterize a RAW file. Many files are uncompressed, while others may use both destructive and lossless compression (and some allow the user to choose). The lack of standardization also means that many files require special software to be opened. RAW image

¹² <https://fileinfo.com/extension/tfw>, last visited 25 August 2022.

	files are sometimes referred to as digital negatives, as they perform the same role as negatives in film photography. I.e., the negative cannot be used directly as an image, but it contains all the information needed to create an image. The preferred format for storing raw image data is DNG.
Recommendations	Not suitable for archiving. Needs to be converted to a format suitable for archiving.

5. Bibliography

Bennett, Michael J (2015). *Evaluating the Creation and Preservation Challenges of Photogrammetry-based 3D Models*. Published Works. 52. http://digitalcommons.uconn.edu/libr_pubs/52

Brown, Adrian (2009). *Digital Preservation Guidance Note 5: Image Compression*. DPGN-05. The National Archives, UK.